

Social Ethos and Removal of Social Inequities in British India -1920's-1947 - A Critical Study

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Abstract

Indian society which has a long history of thousands of years has some malice against few disadvantaged in the society. Society based on its traditional customs and practices was divided on Varna basis, segregated its lower castes and neglected its women. Coming of modernity brought several intended changes bringing a sense of equality, hereby the rulers had to bring forth legislative reforms to enforce change bringing equality. It was made possible by the support reformers and reform movements which was influenced by European concept of equality.

Introduction

Rise of twentieth century India was a plethora of ups and downs, intellectual fervor added with ideals of social inequities, contradictions of high rise society with concept of high level performance and darker side of social inequities that burdened the society.

India the land of ancient culture with glorious past which has rich contribution in the field of divinity, ways of attaining moksha, philosophy, literature, science, art, the list goes on. But there was darker side for it. It neglected the principle of co-living. A part of the society was neglected. Social hierarchy practiced for centuries had left a larger section of its cohabitants neglected, who lived their lives in dejection and deprivation. Secondly its womenfolk either of high caste or low caste were segregated, ill treated and pushed to play a second rate citizens. In this context it is justifiable to observe how twentieth century India reacted to the clarion call of social equality. Through this paper I intend to make a critical analysis of the efforts made by Indians both in individual capacity, organizational capacity and through governmental efforts to eradicate the inequalities that existed: both gender and caste based. As the subject is too vast I am limiting myself to few related issues only.

Twentieth century heralded the idea of equality to the foremost. It was the continuation of nineteenth century. St. Simon, Fourier, Engels, and Marxist ideas of social equality, contributed largely by industrial growth and rise of labour class as a strong work force. Communism grew against the background of exploitative capitalism and colonization.

Inequities were common to most of the societies. No society was an exception. Till the arrival of modern age inequalities were the common order as one or the other form of inequality did exist in all societies. Rich-poor, high-low, noble-serf, slave-freeman, black- white. Along with hierarchical divisions, no society treated its woman better: western or eastern. Gender inequality was a common feature to all the societies. Beginning of neo socialism in twentieth century propagated equality of all. It heralded a clarion call against slave trade, gender inequalities, and inequalities of any kind.

Indian has an extraordinary case of inequalities in all sectors, in all stages. Both gender and caste based hierarchical disparities existed in Indian. No section of the society can be seeing bereft of inequality. Indian society was split both horizontally and vertically. No wonder India which was on the path of rapid change due to close proximity to the European world through British Empire had to accept its weak social connections: both gender and caste based inequalities. That too caste based hierarchy was permanent feature without a chance of change. Because in other societies, those who were in the lower rung, had a chance of coming up due to social upward mobility provided to them. But in India lower castes never given a chance to improve their social position.

Though it seemed a permanent feature with both with religious and social sanctions, everything set to change, it was law of change that explicitly followed. Indian context of social change was mainly based on two streams: they are treatment of its women and caste based inequity.

Gender Inequalities

Naturally the foremost concern was shown towards emancipation of its womenfolk. Women that too women of higher castes suffered much. Restrictions, impositions in the name of social and religious practices were the cause of their sufferings. Ram Mohan Roy, the harbinger of social and religious change was the pioneer in social reform used both institutionalized and individual measures for the removal of Sati. His pioneering efforts did change the society.

Ram Mohan Roy along with his friends carried on a relentless struggle against the abolition of Sati. He was the harbinger of social change in India. Abolition of sati in 1829 was a milestone in the removal of some of the social evils that bothered the society. It paved way for further reforms such as Widow Remarriage Act 1856, Prohibition of Female Infanticide 1872, signified the necessity public participation and governmental support.

The social ethos were so deep rooted and had religious sanctions, a single effort could not have solved in single measure. The problems were numerous: Sati, child marriage, forced widowhood, dowry, polygamy, infanticide were a blot on the social structure of India. Surprisingly they were followed for centuries without being questioned. Removal of these practices needs a courageous social leadership that should come from within. A plethora of institutions, persons came forward to look into the task of removal of these social evils and to efface the stigma that was stuck on Indian society.

Efforts of social reformers of nineteenth century were able to partial removal of few of the evils like sati. But many of the problems still persisted. Inequities of gender and caste remained untouched. They needed a firm handling. It required multidimensional effort to overcome those strongly propagated, deep rooted hard to remove.

Gender inequalities was most harsh and several inhuman practices like sati (still persisted), child marriage, dowry, infanticide, forced widowhood, polygamy (kulinism of Bengal) were the different forms of discrimination of its women. Social organizations, like Brahma Samaj, Widow Remarriage societies, support of women's organizations, Mahila Sanghas, work of reformers like Ishwarchandra Vidyasagar, Pandita Ramabai, M.G.Ranade, D.K.Karve, Veerasha Lingam and several others raised strong voice in support of for the removal of evils that troubled the women folk.

Country that was ruled by a foreign power had lesser voice in government. But our British rulers were more liberal compared to more orthodox leadership in religious and social fields. Support of the government was visible as it accepted the demand for reforms more frequently.

Age of Consent Bill 1891

Child marriage that was rampant in Indian society was strong deterring for the uplift of its womenfolk. Women were most disadvantageous by this practice. Due to early marriage they were pushed to early motherhood at the tender age of twelve or thirteen. Child marriage, marriage of little girls with aged men leading to intercourse even before their puberty was more inhuman practice leading to death of hundreds of young girls. The demands of the reformists and official findings made the government to pass the Age of Consent Act in 1891. Actual procedure of the Act was in discussion for a long time. Starting from 1874 the Procedure of the Bill was in forefront of the social media, newspapers and in Bombay High court in the case of Rukmabai case. Final stroke came after the death of a young girl Phumonidevi in Bengal. It was just humanitarian measure by the government. It was supported by several reformist as well as newspapers. Behramji Malbari was in the forefront of the movement in support of passing of an age limit for marriage of girls. It can be stated that for the reformers courts was armour in their struggle against the upper caste Hindu custom 4.

The Act was strongly protested by orthodox as they found it as a interference by the foreign government in their social practices 5. Balagangadhar Tilak opposed it as he found it: “we would not like that government should have anything with regulating our social customs or ways of living’ 6. Such was the condition which provides a gloomy picture of social change in India. But emergence of twentieth century brought drastic change.

The Act was an amendment to Indian Penal Code as the Act prescribed criminal procedure for violation of the act. But it was not seriously implemented as the government did not like to face the social opposition of the orthodox.

But the government was not in mood to follow these acts with further reform. It did not wish to have backlash of the orthodox. Tilak was in the forefront of criticizing government’s interest in modulating social traditions. Not a surprise the British government expected the strong motivation for reform should come from Indian leadership

Gandhian struggle for independence brought a large number of women into the forefront. Gandhiji’s idea of equality provided a wide space for women in all sectors. He had a firm belief that any social change should come from through emancipation of women. He was able to bring issues of women’s rights and family law reform to the limelight 7. It a recorded fact at no given time (including modern days) such a large number of women emerged on public platforms. Not that they fought for political rights, but primarily they struggled social injustices and worked for bringing a comprehensive code regulating marriage, divorce, and other related issues

Sarda Act 1929

Har Bilas Sarda was a private member in Central Legislature, who introduced this Bill. It was introduced in the form of Child Marriage restraint Act or famously known as Sarda Act. It was the beginning of several social legislations in British India. It opened a Pandora box of women’s issues to the forefront, culminating in changing the legal position of women. Rights of women were guaranteed by a set of laws which was taken up by the imperial government, followed by Presidencies. Few states like Mysore were ahead of the movement to provide justice to its women.

All India Women's Conferences

The nationalist leaders were for treating women justly. They supported the cause of women. National Congress which provided a wider platform for women also helped them to organize themselves. One such organization was All India Women's Conference. It was started by Captain Laxmi. She was a strong propagandist of women's rights called for a women's conference at national level to discuss the numerous problems faced by women. She was able to organize a Conference of women in All India level. She had realized that nothing better will come out of the male dominated members of Legislative Assembly. Thus she decided to a strong vocal force for women's rights. her efforts were supported by congress leaders Kamaladevi Chattopadhyaya, Sarojinidevi Naidu, Muthulaxmi Reddy, Begum Shah Nawaz and others.

This act of nation building inclusive of its womenfolk was an essential part of modernizing India. Educated men sympathized with women to remove the several restrictions on women. General awareness among educated class, role of Newspapers is praiseworthy. 'Amrit Bazar Patrika', 'The Hindu', 'Bombay Chronicle', 'Economic and Political Weekly', and several regional language magazines and periodicals started a strong movement for women's rights

Such was the force of these women leaders, All India Congress during its annual sessions ratify the resolutions of AIWC. But when Congress governments came to power in 1937, they did pass the legislations in provinces with limited scope for women's rights. Thus even congress disappointed the women with their lack of sensibility.

Mahila Samajas, Mandals, Women organizations were organized and effectively working towards emancipation of women during the period were consciously spreading awareness among men and women towards socially-religiously imposed restrictions on them. Widow houses were established in several places. Widow Remarriage societies were organizing marriages for widows. The social concern expressed through these acts and pressure built upon the government through organizations that were working for widow remarriage, raising the age of marriage, prohibiting polygamy, banning of female infanticide led to asset of laws passed in Legislative Assembly. Initiative taken by Har Bilas Sarda and his friends brought set of laws to protect women's rights. Starting from 1929 a set of legislations were passed to help the women to gain property rights, and legal status to widows, unmarried daughters.

But what women could get was just a portion of what they were demanding. The strong fundamentalists influence lack of awareness among women themselves, superstitions and blind belief kept the women of India in the shackles of male dominated, society. They have to wait for independent India's Social legislations of 1950' s to provide them with social justice.

Caste Inequalities

Social inequities based on caste system led to unequal division of the society. Hierarchy it created was artificial and unwanted, but surprisingly it had religious sanctions. As stated earlier they needed firm handling with strong public support . 'Caste' means race or kind, which is derived from Portuguese word 'Casta'⁸.

Whereas Max Weber defines caste or class as a group of persons occupying same class status or in the same class situation'.⁹ As stated earlier every society has one or the other form of inequality. But Indian context it is its rigidity and socio-religious sanction left it untouched for centuries¹⁰.

Cruelty of Indian Varna system was it did not allow a part of the society to participate in any social or religious activities. The untouchables were kept out of the society, lived outside its cities, towns and villages, never considered a part of the mainstream. The concept of 'pure' and 'unpure', segregation as 'touchables' and 'untouchables' divided the Indian society vertically, making part of the society inactive. Vindictiveness of the system is such it never allowed the untouchables to come

up in life, or to gain upward mobility. For centuries the varna system remained as such without any change. One of the effects of this system is it formalized discrimination against the lower castes in the name of religious sanctions.

Coming of the Europeans and their example of egalitarian society made many social thinkers to ponder over changing Indian caste structure. But they did not dare enough to ace the onslaught of the religious sanction and social stigma attached to it. Many social reformers of the nineteenth century were sympathetic about the pitiable condition of the untouchables. The Britishers and missionaries though sympathetic about the harsh treatment of the untouchables, they hesitated to bring any law regarding it, as it was strongly opposed by the caste Hindus. Thus the dalits had to wait for the emergence of their own leaders to can tackle the draconian social practices and to plead for suitable treatment at least by the government. British rule was against any sort of discrimination. They tried to equalize the social justice. But they were not willing to face opposition of the majority who preferred to follow the system as it was. The strong social stigma attached to untouchables tied them to eternal bondage. The sympathetic British could do little to emancipate the dalits. They have to wait for a longer period for their emancipation.

Indian Penal Code and Indian Criminal Procedure were the first effort by the British to bring the concept of equality in India. Through these Codes the British Government implemented uniform laws applying o all discriminating none. But here again the Hindu Code was applied to others who so far retained their separate identity. The tribes, other groups had their own set of laws were grouped under Hindu Code which was based on ancient texts. Indirectly same set of rules which divided the society unequally was given prime place by law courts¹¹.

In this context it is the Caste Disabilities Removal Act of 1850 was the first law through which the British tried to provide justice to the caste discriminated lower castes¹². Nevertheless they did pass this Act with an ulterior motive of helping the coverters to Christianity. Probably for this reason the Hindu fundamentalists protested against the law. Starting from this Act, every acts of the government was suspected.

Jyothibha Phule and Satyashodak Sangh

Foremost voice of the dalits came from Maharastra where Jyothibha Phule himself a crusader for dalit rights, worked towards spreading education among the dalits to awaken from their centuries old slumber. His Satyashodak Sangh under which he organized likeminded people who wished to bring change. He mobilized the dalits, and organized Conferences. His was the beginning of Dalit movement in India. But his was a feeble voice and it did not get suitable support. His own people were too meek to raise their voice in support of him. It is only few educated dalits, Christian Missionaries and few educated upper caste supported it. One such person was Sahu Maharaja of Kolahpur.

Depressed Classes Conferences

By 1919 Act the British Indian government decided to give reservations to Muslims and the Sikhs, but it did not include the most disadvantaged dalits in it. Based on it educated dalits started an awareness program. Depressed classes Conferences were organized in several places. M.C.Raja of Madras province was strong votary of organized struggle to gain their suitable place in the society. There was a inner conflict among dalit leaders. Many of them considered the English as their saviors, did not support national congress as it was dominated by upper castes.

Mahatma Gandhi and his Harijan Upliftment

Gandhiji included the concept of Harijan welfare as one of the program of Non-Cooperation. He advocated the policy of conciliation towards the uplift of the Harijans. His strong support tilted the upper castes towards treating the dalits on compassionate grounds. But he had his own limitations as he never tired to come out the framework of Hindu religion,¹³ Gandhiji had his own mission eradication of untouchability: through removal of caste . He even wrote an article ‘Caste must go’. He preferred to encourage inter caste marriages and inter-dinning’¹⁴.

His was a constructive way to build the gap between the untouchables and the upper castes. His followers established Harijan Sevak Sanghas to indulge in constructive work of regaining the confidence of the untouchables to make them to join the mainstream

Round Table Conference 1930-32

The great turning point in recognition of the dalits as a power group was the nomination of dalit leader B.R.Ambedkar as the representative of the dalits to R.T.C. held at London voice the demands of the untouchables. Ambedkar as sole representative of the dalits demanded a separate electorate and reservation for the dalits. But the discussion remained inconclusive.

Dr.B.R.Ambedkar Is a strong votary of social justice. His was a relentless struggle against the inequality and social segregation of untouchables. He stood for segregation of the dalits from the mainstream Hindus . It is this question of having separate identity for dalits led to differences of opinion between Gandhiji and Ambedkar through Poona Pact 1932. British were eager to appease the dalits by accepting the demand of Ambedkar for separate electorate, keeping aside prescribed number of seats for dalits. Gandhiji did not accept the division of Hindus as dalits and upper castes. He felt it as a ploy of the British ‘divide and rule’. Even B.R.Ambedkar did not expect a revolutionary change in Indian social order and new that there are several supporters of caste¹⁵. Somehow both the leaders decided to solve the issue between them. Ultimately, Poona Pact brought some solution to the problem. But the provisions of the 1935 Act were not seriously implemented. Like in the case of women the dalits had to wait for the drafting and adopting of constitution to emancipate them and for equal treatment it is the independent India that brought a constitutional remedy. However Indian society was slow to react positively for this much needed social change. To conclude Indian society was full of contradiction of high moral ground and spirituality. However it had jeopardized its concept of equality. Though inequality was common, Indian society had showed deep rooted malaise against its women and major chunk of its lower castes. If gender inequality put large section of its women disadvantaged and ill-treated, caste hierarchy divided the society vertically and kept a portion of the population outside the purview of progress and development. Coming of modern age under the British, western education was a strong tool to bring the concept of equality to Indian society. .

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